

Performance Art; Resistance, Framework and Material Realisation

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Introduction

This essay will start by attempting to carve out performance art from Goffman's Dramaturgy framework present in *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (1956). I will examine performance art through the absences of political resistance within Goffman's framework. The themes of resistance, defiance, and retaliation are absent in Goffman's comparison between theatre and the presentation of our everyday selves. When Goffman's *impression management* fails, this 'failing' to uphold the impression becomes part of my performance art framework that is detailed in this essay. The defiance of performative roles and archetypes presented in Goffman's ideologies are shown, both in sources of the 1950s examples and also in the contemporary performances and social interventionists works of William Pope L. and Poppy Jackson – both of whom are mentioned and discussed in the essay.

Performance Art could allow people, from various backgrounds, a way of expressing their knowledge in real-time. Embodied knowledge could be expressed through body actions, creating disruptive presences where forms of self-knowing might otherwise be inaccessible. As a working-class artist and student with severe dyslexia; performance has allowed me to express myself and my knowledge directly with an audience and crosshatch themes in a non-linear and non-discursive manner in a live social context whilst building performative conversation with collaborators (public audiences can also be considered as co-collaborators). My performance art bridges the space between the personal - the internal with the external - the social.

I am often non-verbal in my performance art; yet gestures, material choices and actions can communicate an embodied cognition. My mind is often a prisoner to my brain, but not my body - they seem to be as one. I am then able to think and practice research on my own terms, and access learning whilst disseminating what the body-brain knows.

Throughout the essay I make expressive notes that break up the lineage formula of conventional essay writing, to create a language that corresponds with the disruptive nature of my performances. Sometimes these sentences seem random, but they connect the self within a context of a larger analysis. I am inspired by artists books, such as William Pope.L's book *The Friendliest Black Artist in America*, (2002) where Pope.L cross hatches poetry, thought process and internal dialogue within a larger narrative. I am currently experimenting with various structures and will take this practice into my PhD writing, with the aim of formulating my own, research structures both within practice and in written thesis through a fluid connection, this essay experiments with early examples of this practice.

This essay will demonstrate a variety of themes, confrontation, resistance, class, disruptive presences, and identity that I will look at in more depth throughout the course of my PhD.

Gestalt

Gestalt psychology, as summarised by Bustamante, is ‘a school of thought that seeks to understand how the human brain perceives experiences. It suggests that structures, perceived as a whole, have specific properties that are different from the sum of their individual parts’ (2020). Applied to performance art, Gestalt is made up of previous experiences, recently read information and the body as a structural component that provides a circulatory system between and within parts, expressing an amalgamated language. In this, each part is greater than its sum due to their fluid interaction and, whilst personal, it extends to the environment through conversations and performance in public settings. These extended parts feedback and the sum is never exactly quantifiable. Here the Gestalt of performance art is displayed below in similar terms to a manifesto, “Gestalt” because it is more of a fluid network and progressive understanding – building and remodeling meaning rather than a declaration set by a manifesto.

Performance art

- Synonymous with experience, something that cannot be replicated or reproduced.
- Malfunction is a term I describe when Goffman’s *impression management* (1956) fails, and we see beneath the surface.
- An experience that changes and morphs within the viewer, or participant or performer these roles can become indistinguishable - only then to be reenacted in different forms, a constant evolving language, non-captive research method

- Knowledge is ever evolving and multi-perspective, performance disperses this. It is the antithesis to positivist thinking. Untethered, 'into the realm of invisibility and the unconscious where it eludes regulation and control,' (Phelan, *Unmarked*, 1993, pg.148)
- Knowledge can be expressed through actions/movement without the requirement of permanent form. Not everything is documentable.
- Once unfolded onto the eyes in real time, it cannot be 'corrected' – this opens up possibilities for new discoveries for both performer and audience or participants.

Performance is indeterminate

- When this quality is celebrated the practitioner can produce new results.

Performance art is not a medium

It challenges conventional notions of art and identity, often producing poststructuralist outcomes. Poststructuralism rejects fixed meanings and hierarchical systems of knowledge. Performance art, through its focus on embodiment, temporality, and the relationship between the artist and the audience, disrupts traditional structures and opens up possibilities for alternative interpretations and understandings.

- Undirected thought process
- Movement unlocks what the body knows but cannot speak

Open loose framework. No rehearsals. No preconceived ending. Embrace happenstance and the unpredictable. Process is more important than the result.

All art is performative, not all art is performance art. All art is produced by activity; usually this activity is hidden or embedded in the material. In Performance Art, the activity **is** the art.

Performance artist – definition depends on artist. An ever-changing, evolving medium. A conduit of knowledge. A failed actor.

Me as a performance artist - A failed sculptor who fails to make solid forms.

Ontology – Spirit transference. Performance has an inner unresolved world.

Medium or material – has agency, an inner world.

Picking up material – material converges with the body. Creating a complex ontology, removing objects and material as something known to something unknown, malleable, discovering it in real-time. Activity contests the material as something that is a given, forming new relationships.

Time-based – existing for a set period. Although the memories and embodiment of performance does not disappear completely

What remains? - its elusive and impossible to pin down exactly, it can manifest into different forms

Bodily-cognition – referring to the method and the specific ontology of my performances

4E cognition – Embodied, Embedded, Enacted and Extended (Albert Newen, Leon De Bruin, Shaun Gallagher, 2018)

The child – Spit back. The primal scream.

The complete abandonment of the child is dangerous. Those that have abandoned their child are either depleted of spirit or those that have the most gross amount of control and power.

Political Violence – Acts that promote an elitist jump in wealth at the fatal cost of the general population (recent conservative party).

AI Love – slow death of connection due to technological dependency.

Silent horror – A dystopian contemporary turn. Lack of empathy, and a growing detachment to the body and other people as flesh earthlings with feelings and desire for connection.

Error – potential discovery. Unlike the traditional notion of error, I see error as a potential discovery or new finding, that could be explored rather than dismissed. A possible language in waiting.

Naivety – unique artistic style, something to be held onto. If this quality is kept after years of education it is something that sets artists apart and celebrates individuality. Unfortunately, this child-like quality/originality is often educated out of the pupil.

Conjunctures

To begin, I will attempt to find the 'conjunctures' (Thorsby, 2023) between performance art and the concept of acting. My focus will be on Goffman's dramaturgy theory present in *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (1956), due to his parallels between 'Theatre' and 'Everyday Life'. I am applying Derrida's notion of *Différance* (1960), to carve out performance art through the absence of defiance and resistance in Goffman's sociological comparison between theatre and the presentation of self in the everyday. Performance art; the element of political resistance, the *conjuncture* between acting and everyday life, between activism and art.

... *Performance art begins when the acting dissipates*

In Goffman's preface, he defines *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*, (1956) as a handbook, 'where the sociological perspective from which social life can be studied, especially the kind of social life that is organised within the physical confines of a building or plant. A set of features will be described which together form a framework that can be applied to any concrete social establishment, be it domestic, industrial, or commercial.'

Goffman's Dramaturgy framework consists of a clear division between *Frontstage* and *Backstage*;

Frontstage – applied to social interaction from the world of theatre is about providing an impression so the audience, whether that is colleagues or friends perceive you in a certain way. The impression is to gain favour.

Impression Management – usually occurs *frontstage*, this is where we provide an impression favourable to our social setting. The clothes we may pick for work, the way we comport ourselves in certain social situations. Impression management is described as a ‘delicate’ thing (pg.36). That could unravel and expose us to who we really are (Goffman,1956).

Backstage - the *backstage* deemed as the more private areas of our lives – where the organisation and technical preparation needed to make *frontstage* work occurs, and were we retire when the act is over.

Summary of Goffman’s Theory

In *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*, (1956), Goffman employs a framework where individuals are likened to actors and society is portrayed as a stage. As the actors engage in dialogue and interact with one another, they are guided by the norms and values that govern their roles as members of society.

Différance

Derrida’s *Différance* (1960) is difficult to explain as when meaning is given to shape the term this can undo its promise of being between things. As explained by Mark Thorsby in his YouTube essay *Jacques Derrida: Différance* (2023); *Différance* is more of a ‘movement’ than a word that defines difference in the binary sense, it challenges Claude Levi-Strauss’ structuralism based on the notion that words are given meaning only through other words alone, this usually implies

a positive/negative given to the meaning of words, constructed through their opposite such as hot and cold (Thorsby, 2023). *Différance* as explained by Thorsby 'is between hot and cold,' (2023) the temperature is somewhere between hot and cold but not implied as an exact medium.

Ironically when *Différance* is applied in writing it may appear as a term which is what it attempts to evade, in my first draft of this essay I attempted to apply *Différance* at the end in the conclusion so that the reader could create their own associations between paragraphs about my family dynamics and Goffman's framework, however, this approach was unintelligible to both the reader and myself. In my second attempt although again I recognise the irony of applying *Différance* as the absent marker in Goffman's comparative analysis, therefore somewhat defining it. I ask the reader to acknowledge forms of political resistance as the 'conjuncture,' (Thorsby, 2023) the missing space in Goffman's analysis, rather than a foil that exposes a binary definition between acting and performance. Goffman's work is not specifically speaking about acting per se, throughout *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*, (1956) Goffman provides examples of how certain concrete spaces make 'social actors' perform and how actors' performativity varies between *backstage* and *frontstage* (Goffman, 1956). What he fails to address is retaliation, political resistance, and preservation of the self. This is the space, *conjuncture*, Derrida's *Différance* (1960) that I attempt to address. I also hope the reader may find 'breath' between words and meaning - what I like to imagine as Derrida's *Différance* throughout the essay, on their own terms and through non-linear narrative disruptions within the text.

Resistance

Goffman argues that individuals within a community frequently modify their outward presentation to align with their social interactions. This can involve downplaying one's wealth or adopting behaviors, as explained by Goffman on page 25:

'[I]n fact, however, many classes of persons have had many different reasons for exercising systematic modesty and for underplaying any expressions of wealth, spiritual strength, or self-respect. The ignorant, shiftless, happy-go-lucky manner which Negroes[sic] in the Southern States sometimes felt obliged to affect during interaction with whites illustrates how a performance can play up ideal values which accord to the performer a lower position than he covertly accepts for himself' (Goffman, 1956).

In *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (1956), Goffman omits the ways in which society members challenge stereotypes and deviate from predetermined roles, and also misses the significance of self-preservation and the practice of political resistance in the 1950s and before, such as; Suffragette's movement (early 1900s), the Civil Rights Movement (1954-68) and the Montgomery Bus Boycott (1955-56). The lack of resistance in *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (1956), does not align with the reality of Goffman's era. Goffman's stereotyping of the black man presents a theater archetype of his day. His sociological comparative analysis between theater and everyday life lacks the full complexity and vital aspects of human nature. These fixed notions of people seem to run throughout his book. Another example, Goffman boldly makes the assertion that 'woman is always play-acting'; as the 'inessential other. He goes on

to say that 'she lies when she presents to him an imaginary personage through mimicry, costumery, studied phrases.'(pg.70, 1956). How can woman always play act, when women historically, specifically the suffragettes revolted against the notion of being 'the inessential other' and 'acting for man.'

Fear, oppression, and conformity (the obligation to retain a socially acceptable image) was more prevalent in Goffman's era, however, violence runs throughout history and so does political resistance, excluding it altogether engineers an inaccurate validity to his comparison between theatre and everyday life. Any truth becomes assumption. Goffman's deterministic and insular perspective suggests that individuals are solely influenced by direct interpersonal communication and maintaining impression. However, Goffman overlooks the significance of the internal realm, which operates independently from external observation, and how it intertwines with our interactions and personal experiences that shape individual psychological perspectives, racial disparities, and biases. Goffman's conclusions are based on a narrow range of case studies, which I suspect intentionally avoids addressing political resistance in order to maintain the validity of his own comparison. Today Goffman's concrete walls are less visible - online and offline is less distinct. *Backstage* can look like the *frontstage* or both (Tracey Emin, *My Bed*, 1998). In light of the recent pandemic, the home is simultaneously the place of work. Goffman's work does propose a handful of contemporary question, however – does acting imply that there is a true self? A self that appears *backstage* now that the backstage and front stage are less distinguishable and are people perpetually acting? Or, due to the decline in embarrassment, has the acceptance of individualism risen and depleted the need to act? Rather than taking this dualistic standpoint, I propose that people

are multifaceted and lie between these two posed extremities. People have many evolving and versatile identities that, in turn, are resilient and the self (the heart or child) encompasses these identities.

Embarrassment

Fixed by the 'concrete' buildings that hold them, Goffman's actors in face-to face interactions, seemingly attempt to find a middle ground to avoid embarrassment. Embarrassment is a key factor in *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (1956). It is repeated (29 times) in a relatively short book for a consistent argument to the notion of conforming to social rules and conventions. There is a hyper conservative focus on preserving a role or facing embarrassment, as if that is the only emotion that humans are capable of experiencing. It is one of the only emotions, as well as confusion, that Goffman speaks of in terms of an internal world of a person.

Fig. 1 Poppy Jackson, *Impossible* ,(2014), (a photograph of the artist outside, in the city alleyway)

Embarrassment and modesty that hold up Goffman's framework are less of a contemporary issue. Not everyone becomes embarrassed for slipping on their 'lines' or disrupting the flow. Willam Pope. L *The Great White Way: 22 miles, 9 years, 1 street* (2001 – 2009) and Poppy Jackson's *Impossible, surrounding city alleyways, USA* (2014) show how disruption can lead to an interesting redirectory of the concept of 'embarrassment'.

In Goffman's analogy individuals are likened to actors and society is portrayed as a stage. As the actors engage in dialogue and interact with one another, they are guided by the norms and values that govern their roles as members of society. Jackson disrupts the space between the alleyway by intersecting it with her own body, wearing no underwear, people walk underneath her. This act of defiance changes the physical space in which people are guided challenging the norms and values that usually govern an alleyway. Members of society are forced to reevaluate norms that are usually held within a particular space, this rupture of the norm would cause embarrassment, but Jackson in this example who is acting against the conformity is void of embarrassment, therefore challenging the status quo of what would be considered as 'embarrassing.'

Fig. 2 William Pope.L, *The Great White Way* (22 Miles, 9 Years, 1 Street) 2001-2009.

William Pope L.'s *The Great White Way*, is a 9-year performance/social intervention of the artist wearing a superman costume as he crawls along Wall Street. Pope.L's disruptive presence is simple; he crawls instead of walks and wears a superman costume - these two distinct diversions, from what is considered as the norm, is both passive (in terms of non-violent) yet powerful because Pope.L does not adhere to what may be considered by society as 'embarrassing.' His spirit triumphs over the social construct of conformity, undermining businesspeople in suits.

That is where the hole lies in Goffman's comparison between theatre and everyday life. Active diversion. *Breathing* attributes of political resistance.

Rather than feeling 'embarrassment,' during his piece *The Great White Way: 22 miles, 9 years, 1 street* (2001 – 2009), William Pope L. subverts the conversation by stating 'At one point I realized that talking to people when you're laying down on the street is a moment, you don't get to do that very much. And people, they'll talk to you differently when they're standing up over the top of you. They think

they're like instant superiority. Except in this case, I have the super suit.' (Pope L., Moma interview, n.d)

Error

Error = potential discovery...

My framework is influenced by Goffman's *Impression management*, in contrast to Goffman my framework encourages the shattering of 'de rigueur,' (pg.36, 1956) as a form of deeper meaning.

Goffman acknowledges that *Impression Management* is delicate:

'...[a]s students we must be ready to examine the dissonance created by a misspelled word, or by a slip that is not quite concealed by a skirt; and we must be ready to appreciate why a near-sighted plumber, to protect the impression of rough strength that is de rigueur in his profession...we must be prepared to see that the impression of reality fostered by a performance is a delicate, fragile thing that can be shattered' (pg.36, 1956).

My performance art framework embraces what Goffman's social actors attempt to conceal. This framework embraces the female blight of nudity (Emma Starkey, *Clown White walks* 2016-2017). The misspelled word and its potential affect. The new sound - a language not limited by the rules and functions of a known word (Meredith Monk, *Do You Be*, 1971). A drawing full of "errors" with no erasure, (Alberto Giacometti, *Studies of Diego*, 1962). It is in this *error*, that otherworldly embodiments appear.

Fig.3 Alberto Giacometti , *Studies of Diego*. [Red ballpoint pen and pen and ink on paper], (1962)

In Giacometti's *Studies of Deigo*, (1962), you feel the weight of Giacometti's heads because of these "errors," energetic lines. By failing to use an erasure he sculps the head drawing it out from the paper, his pencil marks exceed the 2D of paper. Monk's *Do You Be*, (1971) transcends the ordinary function of a word, pulled into vagueness, and yet familiarly primal - its sound embodies a language non conducive to the constructs of the written/spoken word. <https://youtu.be/89I-4wtz3uU?feature=shared>

Fig. 4 Meredith Monk, *Do You Be* (1971)

Performance, in a strictly ontological sense, occupies this space of potential error. It unfolds on the eye in real time, and there is no edit. Performance art attempts to shatter the impression of reality. It takes the individual's presence and being into perspective.

In everyday life there are instances when the pretence slips, and you are able to see a person as a multifaceted human. Through exposing our flawed nature, a likability may occur rather than upset. In life, this can be garnered with a laugh - both parties may laugh spontaneously, recognising that the pretence once held in a situation has dissipated. I do not know if the same can be said for plays, as

usually a play is a return of a previous narrative, a love of the characters is what builds such expectations. The unexpected can lead to bad reviews. I do not know if the same can be said for real life. In life, in practice, the stage is broken down and the expectation of a play is not as present. Unlike Goffman's need to preserve 'de rigueur,' (pg.36,1965) For me, performance begins in the malfunction, the slippage, resistance and not confide to an art context. The cashier slipping on her lines.

It is when the body revolts to free the mind.

A key factor of performance art is confrontation and rebellion, social engagement, and challenging the norms imposed by institutions on individuals. This approach is not just practiced in the arts but within everyday life. Anyone that implements resistance also asserts a performance art paradigm. Public live work leads to mixed community involvement, and therefore segmented physical spaces fundamental to Goffman's ideologies are disrupted. The idea of *frontstage*, *backstage*, audience and performer become blurred. The performer/audience dynamic is often indistinguishable, unlike a traditional play where audience watch the stage at a distance, shrouded in the dark. Social interventions and performance art sets itself apart from traditional theatre by refusing to adhere to a conventional storyline, employing random or chance-based frameworks, and directly engaging with the audience. Essentially, it embraces life's disruptions and utilises them as a form of deeper communication involving unexpected variables – what I refer to as *slips* or *errors* that open the artist, community, and society to new possibilities.

In my framework, performance is both the front and back stage and this is where the trial and errors exist. There are no *backstage* preparations. There are no rehearsals and experimentation is live. It reflects my childhood in this regard - there was no room for preparation in my mother's house. Preparation required a safe space, and I lived moment to moment. My current home, a place of rebellion and expression is found in my body, in the gallery and in the landscape rather than a domestic setting. Resistance and confrontation occur on this diminished stage. Due to my economic situation, the studio; which is typically known as the *backstage* to the gallery (*frontstage*); is often fleeting and more recently the social environment incorporating both stages or simply no definitive stage. There is nowhere to practice, and therefore it encourages a sense of immediacy in the work and the room for "error" results in spontaneous occurrences, that in turn may prove to be a source of originality/contribution to knowledge.

...I am a failed actor, unable to rehearse my lines I go out into this world naked.

Due to a lack of *frontstage* preparation and no definitive stage, I approach practice unclothed. The power is in the vulnerability of such exposure, performing acts that cannot be corrected, tapping into a past, an inner self that I should feel ashamed of, but I do not. The confrontational elements of my past and the working-class archetype that is often assigned to me along with other social personas are inverted through practice. Through the live body, I reclaim

Fig. 5 Emma Starkey *Clown #2*, c-type print on Dibond, (2018)

my autonomy.

Fig. 6 Samuel Fosso, *The lifeguard*, (1997)

Akin to artists such as Samuel Fosso, with his work *The lifeguard*, (1997) and *The Chief, the one who sold Africa to the colonialists*, (1997), and Coco Fusco and Guillermo Gómez-Peña, *Two Undiscovered Amerindians Visit Madrid*, (1992), and Signe Pierce and Alli Coates', *American Reflexxx* (2015). These artists confront the viewer through maximising stereotypes challenging the viewer to observe their own absurd assumptions.

Performance Art Model - Embryotic cell

Fig. 7 Performance Art Model, *Embryotic Cell*, (2023)

My performance art model is inspired by a human cell. The circle emulates the membrane wall of the cell, its semi-permeable wall is autonomous and semi-selective, the thin wall allows the cell to evolve yet remain unabsorbed by its environment (Kara Rogers, 2023). The model is referred to as an embryotic cell, it is in the early developmental stage and can transform throughout and beyond its initial appearance – the possibility is found within and outside the cell, its semi

permeable wall allows for such development. The model incorporates Deleuze and Guattari rhizomic concept, 'A rhizome has no beginning or end; it is always in the middle, between things, interbeing, intermezzo.' (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987, pg.25)

The model is meant to be seen from a birds-eye point of view and has multiple entry/exit points (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). Each element; picking up object, context, dissolving the stage and environment/social, work fluidly together. Performance art's vaporous ephemerality becomes fluid as what it disperses does not disappear completely, elements return changing through a reflective analytical cycle, it is remodeled along with newer elements consistently going through a non-hierarchical symbiotic process.

The model encompasses 4E cognition - Embodied, Embedded, Enacted, and Extended (Andy Clark and David Chalmers,1998), (Shaun Gallagher, Leon De Bruin, Albert Newen, 2018).

4E cognition as described by Shaun Gallagher in his interview hosted by Mangalam Research Center;

'[W]hat is the prevalent model of cognitive in Cognitive science today?

S.G: There is a prevalent model of cognition in cognitive science today and it's dominated for quite a while, that goes back to the origins of cognitive science in the computational context, so that is a model of the mind that involves computational processes, it's very much brain centered. The phrase in the head type of processes that basically locate the mind in the head or in the brain, and

the idea there, is that one can explain all there needs to know about cognition in terms of brain processes.

What is 4E cognition and how does it challenge the prevalent model?

4E cognition is made up of *Embodied, Embedded, Enacted, and Extended* the main message there, is that cognition is not just in the head , it's something that involves the body in general and also the situation of the body in the environment, so, the unit of explanation is not just neuronal processes in the brain but the whole complex of brain-body-environment taken as a whole or something like a gestalt. Where there are dynamical relations among those different elements, that have to be taken into account of we want a better concept of cognition.'(2017)

Throughout this section of the essay, I will examine the terms *embodied, embedded, enacted, and extended* through a performance lens and provide examples of previous practice that cross textualise Gallagher's notion of 4E cognition (2018), with my performance art model (2023).

Pick up object

Embodied , 'The idea that the brain co-evolves with the body,' Gallagher, (2018).

Picking up object – This practice converges the body (*embodied*) and material (*embodied + embedded*) leading to *extended* material thinking. I often refer to performance art as 'doing,' as I do not necessarily see the work as a performance in the traditional sense, but rather gestures, movement, a dance with/in material that is not choreographed. In this approach I start intuitively selecting material to

work with, with either no presuppose plan or a fluid plan. Picking it up can lead to the evolution in the artistic process as seen in *Attempting Omega* (2014).

Fig. 8 Emma Starkey, *Attempting Point Omega* (2014) C-type print on Dibond.

The original thought process for this piece was imagined as a photograph, the antlers tied around my head with thick rope. This was a non-practical idea as the antlers were far too heavy. When I picked up the antlers, I started to gain a relationship with how they operated, as seen in *Attempting Point Omega*, (2014) grey scale photograph. Through moving with the antlers, the piece developed into a Live audience and discreet video. The nature that fed through from the *environment* led to a symphony between movement and sound. Personal meaning *extended* from the origins of the antlers. The *context* of where the antlers/material comes from is an important aspect to my performance practice, its materiality surfaces through the activation of the body. The material is always considered, even if the operation is unknown until the performance takes place/unfolds. The antlers were sourced from a deer sanctuary during the rut

(mating season) a sanctuary may ethically remove antlers if the deer has not yet shed, so that the stag does not accidentally kill the hind (female deer.) It was important to me to either find naturally shed antlers or ethically sourced. I also shaved my hair for the performance as a reciprocal exchange. The *breath* that I associate with Derrida's *Differance* is shown here in the reinvention and operation of the antlers, and the shifting of meaning into the unknown.

Fig. 9 Emma Starkey, *Attempting Omega*, (2014), live performance, and recording.

The model embraces Barrett's material theory, 'the acknowledgement that instruments and objects of research are not passive, but emerge as co-producers in collaborative and, in the case of audiences, participatory approaches that may not be pre-determined at the outset of the research.' Bolt (2016 cited in Barrett 2014, p.3)

Context

Context that is integrated in my PhD are first-hand observation of Reynolds painting as referenced in the MR402 module. The context also *extends* to the social environments of where the performances are situated. The location and settings are often premediated, for their pre-existing frame/context. The interventionist/ performance work aims to disrupt and contest preexisting context and knowledge. In the following paragraphs I will show examples of gallery performances and social interventions, to show how context is applied.

Fig.10 Emma Starkey, *Lady-clown-other*, (2017), performance and video.

For the multimedia performance, *Lady-clown-other* (2017), the gallery space was chosen for its historical context. James Whistler, in 1883 pioneered the white gallery space, as a device to separate himself from the Victorian public. White was instrumentalised by Whistler to ostracise the Victorian people. In his exhibition in which the white space debuted as the 'exclusive colour of the artistic elite,' (James

Fox, 2012) Whistler showcased works that were monochrome, in white frames, even the invigilator was made to wear all white. (Fox, 2012). For me, the white gallery space is austere and capable of elevating all practices, naming it art. The white gallery is not neutral. When a banana duct taped to a white wall (*Comedian*, Maurizio Cattelan, 2019) becomes art, it implies the power within the white wall gallery. Art does have the power to change the white gallery into a space of reimagining, in a duo installation Maurizio Cattelan and Lucio Fontana's, exhibition LA FINE DI DIO, (2014) we view a knelt Hitler (*HIM*, 2001) in front of a large pink egg (*Concetto spaziale, La fine di Dio*, 1963) in this illuminous white space Hitler is suspended in time, forever praying for redemption. To transform this white space from a CONTEMPORARY stark white gallery to an environment of timelessness as in the case of LA FINE DI DIO, (2014) is a testament to the power of art.

Fig.11 Emma Starkey, *Lady-clown-other*, (2017)

Emma Starkey, *Lady-Clown-other*, (2017)

Emma Starkey, *Lady-Clown-other*,(2017) as part of *Post-Trump part i* Exhibition.

In *Lady-Clown-other* (2017) rather than transform the space, I incorporate the stark whiteness into the piece, revealing its historic origins, through applying white clown paint to my face, and unveiling my beige body under a white dress, it destabilises the invisibility of white. The performance dislodges the notion of the white gallery as something neutral. As we have seen in the above examples, white is not simply neutral but is as much of a device as any colour; probably more so because as a colour, its presence often goes undetected. Its *embedded* history was partly *enacted* in the performance through the live body applying white paint to the face and utilising white objects such as a white dress and cotton balls.

The notion of *extended* mind as explained by Gallagher, ‘...is something that develops out of a theory of distributed cognition.’ And can be read in feedback, where a sharing of information takes place. Feedback helps confirm performance's ability to transfer knowledge from what is usually perceived as a cognitively driven process to a unified bodily cognition.

Michael Bryan's review on Emma Starkey's work

April 2017, Five Years, London N19

It's always slightly unnerving to be present in a white cube space, not so much as an ethnically "marked" body as spectator, but the sheer whiteness of the gallery seems to uncomfortably engulf and neutralize whatever power a radically created art piece had outside of it. Which is why the performance by Emma Starkey is an unnerving experience, because of the willingness to accept and embrace the whiteness of the gallery space within and without.

The performance begins with Starkey sat in front of a table with three objects neatly placed. Of these three objects, the face paint is the first to be used, Starkey applying with at first messy, then sensual strokes, slowly disappearing in the process. A pile of cotton wool balls is the second item on the table, this time Starkey chews one ball at a time, saliva leaking from her mouth and occasionally generating a retching reflex. The consumption and wearing of two brightly white objects, accompanied by the stuttering of a digitally slowed-down video displayed alongside the table became a repulsive sight to see.

Punctuating her white facial mask is the third object; a roll of red ribbon tape, slowly unveiled and sensually tied around her neck, the red mirroring the images of blood shown in the video. The performance becomes increasing visceral as Starkey proceeds to shed her white clothing. Standing up, her newly marked face contrasts with the rest of her nude body, causing an disturbing dichotomy of white as object and subject.

The concept of "alien" bodies, present in an unmarked, White space was recently discussed in the book *space invaders* (2003), however author Nirmal Puwar made references to non-White, non-male bodies. The striking thing about Starkey's performance is that she has seemingly achieved the very same effect utilising the colour white. Out of the three objects used, the face paint is significant, because we see a young woman, racially identified in society as White covering her face with bright white paint, disappearing in the process.

Of the books recently written about the concept of whiteness, only two (*Unmarked* by Peggy Phelan and *White* by Richard Dyer) attempt to uncover and unpack its qualities, possibly due to its default societal status it seems to avoid analysis. Seeing a white female artist doing the same within her performances is an unsettling experience, because she dares to question the very foundations of Western society, one in which "whiteness" is seen as the pinnacle of existence.

By Michael S Bryan

Fig.12 Michael Bryan's feedback on *Lady-Clown-Other*, performance at Five Years gallery as part of a performance event Post-Trump part i (2017)

Michael Bryan's feedback shows how my performance art model and how Gallagher's notion of 4E cognition was *enacted* through performance. The combination of material application (*embodied*), previous experiences that the body retains (*embodied*) – such as those that are hard to grasp, background

reading (*embedded in context*) on Whistler and instinctual movement (*enacted*) results in a unique synergy. As demonstrated in Bryan's feedback the performance imbricates knowledge, and also disrupted preexisting knowledge on what is usually perceived as a neutral white gallery space, the performance dislodged its neutrality. Bryan's feedback directly led me to Richard Dyer's book *White*, (2017) [1997]. The performance feedback demonstrates a transference of knowledge. This approach to knowledge sharing may allow for a more inclusive research model. As an artist with dyslexia, I was able to convey and produce new knowledge utilising a bodily cognition. Rather than collecting data then writing up in a traditional mode of research dissemination, it allowed me direct access to explore the body as a medium and disseminate research through non-linguistic communication, a transference of knowledge that is non fixed and unpredictable. The subconscious and the suppressed information that is in memory is often *reenacted* with recently read information, and through the body relationships form that are expressed through gestures, movements, and choices in materials and environment, this method offers alternative readings, beyond the premises of discursive text.

Extended - For the viewer as well as myself it becomes an evolving relationship of knowledge sharing through live experience. The feedback may assist in the performance's absence, as a contribution in an accompanying book – part of the thesis. A multi perspective book displaying a post structuralist notion of meaning/truth, truth as multimedia, multi perspective and knowledge as intersubjective.

Dissolving the stage

Can knowledge be transferred mind to mind, body to body without a form of interface? The artist can dissolve the stage through emerging themselves within everyday context or the context they wish to contest. The line between performer and 'audience' becomes blurred, when the staging evaporates, which can lead to a less authoritative understanding of the world.

Fig. 13 Emma Starkey, *Myopia* (2015) performed at the MAC Birmingham. Photograph taken by Robin Woodward.

Fig.14 Emma Starkey, *Myopia*, (2015) formerly the Worcester Art Workshop (Cellar)

Embedded as described by Gallagher during an interview with Managalam Research Center

...'[e]mbedded usually refers to the body, the body in an environment, coupled to an environment in important ways, that environment is not just physical, it's also social, there are other people out there and it's also cultural in the sense that we often engage in various practices that are often shaped by things and the architectural features...which helps to define different affordances, different possibilities for action' (Gallagher, 2018)

In *Myopia*, (2015) I wore a mottled hood, hospital gown and walked across a sharp candy field, trying to find footing, during which an elderly woman, who came across the work, held my hand and assisted me to clear ground. This unconceived factor added a dimension to the work, and spoke of empathy,

human touch and connection unbound by age or who was underneath the hood. Although this performance was attempted more than once, the environment in which it was performed allowed a varying degree of examples of how the stage dissolves. In the Mac in Birmingham, audience members witnessed the piece as more of a “theatre” event, with one audience member visibly irate and disappointed (as I unintentionally dripped blood on their expensive handbags), whereas at Worcester Arts Workshop in the cellar, the example given above of the elderly lady assisting me gave the piece a whole new meaning and dynamic, giving credence to the *environment* being an integral part of how a work is conceived by the audience.

Social/Environment

Fig.15 Emma Starkey, *Clown White walks* (2016-2017) Photograph taken by Robin Woodard.

Enactive as explained by Gallagher, ‘...is this idea that we are embodied and, in the environment, and that our primary relationship between body and environment is really gear towards action, the idea that we are perceiving the environment in terms of what we can do.’ (Gallagher, 2018)

Social interventions that usually occur in non-traditional art settings allow a greater reach with the community, and often allows unexpected occurrences.

Below is a written extract of the responses from an intervention in December 2016.

‘As I clambered out of the car, I felt the cold pavement on my feet, it grounded me. I started to walk towards the bridge, the repetition of walking - an everyday movement led to ‘being’ the clown rather than performing. A lady looked bemused and simultaneously shocked; she said nothing. I walked towards the Cathedral, during this time I noticed a car bibbing enthusiastically, communicating a recognition, a celebration of the ruptured mundanity. A fleeting reciprocity. A man diverts his gaze. A female jogger passes me laughing. Two morning photographers staring in surprise... A man crosses me ‘Good morning,’ the slight turn up of his lip identifies a confusion between the words and the image unfolding onto his retinas, revealing a preternatural (dis)alignment...’(Starkey,2023)

Gallagher’s notion of *extended* can be read in the responses of members of the public detailed in my notes; the car enthusiastically bibbing, the horn was used as instrument, varying in a musical pattern. This showed how any form of ‘stage’ between us had been broken down and parts of the environment became an

intrinsic part of the work. This interaction also added an element of surprise and celebration, which then lends itself to non-preconceived themes within the work.

People are not deemed as bystanders in the work, but instead are active and often collaborators. The varied social dynamics of outdoor and various nonrelated art spaces can lead to mix community involvement. This could also be celebrated on other non-related art campuses across a university, empty shop units or any public space.

The clown white paint was *enacted* through an embodied movement. Through *movement* associated with Derrida's *Differance*, we see how the material application and the act of the body moving creates new associations/presences that disrupt previous notions of the clown and Worcester Bridge, Religion (Cathedral) and Riverside. These contextual structures destabilise and alter when all of the components set by my model and 4E cognition are at play.

Possibility

Originality is located in the body. If we were to ask a hundred students to take a picture of the same tree, using the same device, not one picture will be the same. A performer can never repeat the exact performance, there will always be slight differences. Therefore, a different body replicating the performance **will** be different. It will never be exact. It is one of the reasons why Marina Abramovic is not concerned about performing other artists work, or performers performing her work.

In Abramovic's recent RA retrospective, the piece *Nude With Skeleton*, (2002,2005,2023) was recreated. It shows a performer on top of a rectangle monitor with a life size Abramovic screened underneath, seemingly working in the same pose and same skeleton. The performer appeared still in comparison to Abramovic's movement. Even though they both occupy the same dimensional space. The slight differences in how both artists worked with the skeleton became monumental and highlighted the originality found in the unique performativity of the body.

Possibility also arises from two or more people experiencing the unknown potentials of an interaction, this occurs live and is unpremeditated.

Materialism and Violence

Sometimes I wake up in a state of dread. Could exploring whiteness through representation and performance art, and contributing towards research be detrimental and perpetuate a certain kind of violence? Similar to Richard Dyer in his book *White*, I have no ambition to contribute towards white studies, but rather through examining whiteness qua white, (2017)[1997] like Dyer but through the lens of a working-class woman I aim to dislodge its power located in its evasiveness, 'making whiteness strange' (Dyer, 2017 [1997], pg4) through my body which encompasses a white - working class dichotomy. I aim to make research where white ideologies become absurd and alien leading to a moment of collapse or it folds in on itself. Similar to when milk splits.

This dread has led me to reevaluate my MR402 assignment. In this assignment I realise that in terms of gaining a stronger reaction the image of the white clown gauges more aggression, especially in newspaper form. It loses its potency which is held in its nuance engagement. The strength is in its ludicrousness and humour, this was reflected back at me during the live intervention. The photograph is a powerful thing, it makes the viewer believe they have seen a performance that they did not witness – the image is the *belief* that the viewer has seen it live rather than seeing it. Through the MR402 module I have come to realise that I have to be careful in terms of preserving the performance. The difference between representing and performance can be the difference between an idea perpetuating violence or not. Practice is different to an idea. Performance is different to a photograph as shown in the MR402 module with the idea of a naked body inciting more complex aggression than an actual naked body as

witnessed in the live performance. Because of the specificity of the subject matter that I am looking at, it is my responsibility as a researcher on how the work will be disseminated, it is not an afterthought. I am looking at Sir Joshua Reynolds as his paintings come under the realm of representation, through the live body in practice can these ideas be undone?

My problem with photography is that it alludes to a resolution that never takes place in performance, as Phelan points out with performance 'its disappearance evades regulation, eventually becoming part of the unconscious.' (Phelan, 1993, pg. 148) For me that is the experience that fails to be documented, the thing that will remain evasive, the bodily-cognition that occurs between people. What Polanyi refers to as 'indwelling', (1997) as time moves on non-recorded performance becomes even more indistinguishable. I am hoping to gain some *sense* of this *indwelling* and mind to mind transference in the form of feedback, images, film, and internal dialogue the aim is not to drown the piece but attempt a balance where the unresolved element comes through in one way or the other. Maybe, this will be dependent on each individual piece and how it is then framed after the event and/or during the event.

Barthes attempts to find an image of his recent deceased mother as discussed in *Camera Lucida: Reflections on Photography*, but cannot find what he refers to as 'punctum,' an attempt to fill the loss. Barthes finds her in a picture before his birth, when she is a child, that is where he finds his mother (1980). Maybe, the unresolved element is found in the loss. The *breath*, the unresolved space between performance and photography, Derrida's *Differance* (1960). In this respect *differance* is looked at as a movement, between experience and material.

How can I make the loss evident, through its incompleteness? Rather than saturating a performance as seen with the many iterations of Clown White walks, (2016-2017) photographs, videos, newspaper seen in the MR402 module. The sheer attempt to grasp the performance as though complete preservation is possible can lead to drowning and the collapse of a performance ontology. Some performances' afterlife could be written part in text. In a few words and a few images. Other performances could be mediated through video or film- with a faint description of internal dialogue. And some may exist in feedback alone. It allows the readers *breathing space* for interpretations, creating an evolution in the reader beyond performance. The *breathing space* attempts Derrida *Differance* (1960) rather than defining meaning, allowing meaning to come to light - through co production (the reader).

In the absence of performance, I will assess on an individual level, each performance what may work best in framing what has been dispersed.

The ontology depends on the artist's practice, medium or non-medium, what remains, what construction replaces the ephemeral act. My ontology/way of working is more attuned with Peggy Phelan's performance ontology (pp.146-166) due to the her focus on living bodies, as discussed, 'performance implicates the real through the presence of living bodies,' (1993), rather than Auslander who is concerned with the photograph as the object of performance as detailed in *The iconic image: a conversation with Philip Auslander*, (2021). However, I am open to exploring other modes of practice. I am in the early stage of my PhD project and have not discovered which method is the best to apply and might be circumstantial on each performance. I lean toward Phelan because my project

investigates how live bodies rupture representation, and her performance ontology is concerned with the live body/bodies.

Conclusion

I started the essay attempting to find the *conjunction* between performance art and acting, specifically Goffman's terms of social acting, which lead to spaces being conceived through absences in Goffman's comparative analysis between theatre and the presentation of self in *Everyday*, these absences, *conjunctions* were proven to be vital for my performance framework. *Resistance*, *Embarrassment and Error* were then examined through varied artistic practices. These themes I intend to take further into my PhD practice/thesis.

Transmutation of a non medium/ live event to physical and permanent medium changes the nature and meaning of the work. If this is not sensitively approached it can lead to important nuances disappearing. Framing the research so that *frontstage* - performance and *backstage* - documentation flow through noninvasive camera equipment and reflective writing will be crucial, blurring/dissolving these stages will retain a level of personal performance ontology rooted in class and family history. Through representations, the conversations could delve into violence as discussed in *Materialism and Violence*. I am apprehensive when photographing or videoing my performance work. As well as this concern the camera as a device disrupts the fluidity of the process for me, the raw undirected element of the work can become eclipsed when the camera is present. As part of going forward I will investigate various less invasive cameras, and work with an experienced team.

Broad analysis, also becomes a major factor expressed and stated in my introduction, through body actions in real time, creating disruptive presences where forms of self-knowing might otherwise be inaccessible. As I am attempting

to challenge ideologies within white, not reinstate them, class, disruption, confrontation, and identity, become key concepts through which to develop a participatory understanding.

The essay may read as dysfunctional when compared to conventional structures of an essay but it highlights a variety of key themes that will be apparent and focused on in more depth and transparency throughout my PhD.

Disruption is present in short spurts of poetry or reflection as seen in this essay on pg.10, 23 and 24 and in the MR402 module exemplified in the quote , '*The motif of the clown seems to belong to me in some way. An entity that has followed me like a shadow, but instead of living on the outside, the shadow lives within...*' (pg.10,2023), this practice thesis's formulation reflects my dyslexia and how I formulate connections, how meaning floats between and within spaces and incorporates Derrida's notion of *Differance* (1960), this expression of language also reflects the disruptive nature of my performance works. Furthering my practice, I will research how other writers apply text in non-conventional ways, I will look at a variation of artist books, as well as authors such as Georges Perec, *Species of Space and Other Pieces* (1974) and Giannina Brasch, *Empire of Dreams*, (1994).

Going forward, I am going to start reintroducing food into my practice as it has economic currency and can spur memory in the viewer or participate of the performance. After a conversation with Dr Ros Jennings, it unearthed something that was said to me in relation to olives. It was inferred that due to my working-class background I would not like olives and that they are an acquired taste. Another recent conversation was with Dr Liz Swift, she spoke about a strange

experience, where Swift viewed an opera piece through a close up on screen while her son simultaneously viewed the performance live at the Royal Opera House theatre, the two perspectives differed substantially. Swift's son could not relate to seeing the strange mouth movements of the opera singer (which was seen by his mother through the screen) as he had been seated within the theatre. These conversations become sources within my future performance practice. Like any malleable material, including conversation, I hope to delve into some aspects of autoethnography through weaving fragmented memories into newer performances. I intend to make a mixture of gallery-based performance art and social practice/interventions in alternative spaces.

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